

VALIDITY OF ADOPTING E-RESOURCES IN SCHOLASTIC LIBRARIES: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT:

This article focuses on the various facets of e-resources and the effectiveness of using e-resources in academic libraries. Digital technology has made application of the stored intellect faster, quicker and more relaxed. This gathered knowledge over the ages has to be used for forthcoming research; social change and overall growth. Electronic assets addresses storage problems and monitor knowledge flow thus digitized print and electronic sources of knowledge are becoming increasingly important to the academic institutes. The introduction of technology has led the libraries introducing new component to their catalog, e-resources are the most popular among them. This paper provides the need of e-resources, benefits of e-resources, effectiveness of e-resources use, types of e-resources and its services, also offers a summary of these assets and explains some benefits and drawbacks.

KEYWORDS:

E-RESOURCES, E-BOOKS, E-JOURNALS E-NEWSPAPER AND E-THESIS.

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INTRODUCTION

Latest technologies have always been of interest to libraries, both for the purpose of enhancing parameter of service and elaborating operational efficiency. Today, libraries of all kinds, whether public, research, academic or special libraries are largely looking forward to implementing emerging technologies, due to their potential for cost savings in operations and management of collections and patrons, often using e-resources. Electronic Resources (e-resources) are the electronic format accessible information that can be accessed through various electronic devices including computers, laptops, mobile devices and tablets. They can also be accessed globally via the internet, or locally (Johnson et al., 2012).

Many types of Digital Content include e-books, e-journals, e-images, other interactive items, and numerical, graphical, or time-based titles that have been written for marketing purposes. The 21st Century is changing rapidly. Through the increasing growth of e-media, libraries not only procure study materials such as printed edition and journals, but also prepare for the online access to different learning services. The library environment is experiencing a rapid and diverse transformation which is leading to a formation of libraries with a focus on e-services. On the one hand, there is a the demand for better library collection in terms of a large amount of resources and, on

the other, the publishing medium is determined to be rigid in accommodating this demand by e-publishing both a lightning speed and online access (Venkadesan, et. al 2004).

The fifth law, that the library is a growing organism (Ranganathan, 2006), mandates that libraries must continue to expand. Perhaps we should look at electronic information and assume that from the perspective of physical space creation is not as urgent, but this is something that libraries are struggling with. In the digital world the analog continues to be important. Publishing books remains fine, and still much affordable than they were in 1931. Libraries will continue managing storage issues. It is expressed in knowledge creation figures as well as the creation of library information services of every kind. Also the emergence of e-resources does not stop the creation of new print content, and has not altered the speed at which they expand.

To the coming years, Lancaster's vision of a fully digital world isn't likely to emerge true. The compromises librarians have to make between book shelf space and electronic terminal space to meet this always-expanding need will continue to be a problem. In consideration of staff and expertise, one can see the library as an expanding organization too. While the library continues to expand in

services, so does the training required to provide these new programs. Perhaps we might argue that both libraries and the librarianship profession are growing organization. The purpose of the fifth law for marketing is to update the library to future consumer needs, namely mobilizing resources, resolving confusion about emerging user needs, new programs, new user groups, new climate, etc.

Lancaster's vision of a completely digital world is unlikely to come to pass in the upcoming years. Librarians will continue to face challenges in balancing the ever-increasing demand for space between electronic terminals and book shelves. The library can also be viewed as a growing institution when taking personnel and expertise into account. The training needed to offer these new programs is growing along with the library's service offerings. One could argue that the profession of librarianship and libraries are expanding organizations. By mobilizing resources, clearing up confusion regarding new programs, new user groups, new climates, etc., the fifth law of marketing aims to update the library to meet the needs of future patrons. The library will also need to update its programs in order to keep up with other global shifts. The library does not step behind when it comes to improving to future technologies. Employees of the library ought to be science-literate. To make more efficient use of such rules, libraries and information facilities need to implement marketing strategies.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To know the Need, Benefits of e-resources usage
- To find out the effective use of the e-resources in libraries
- To Identify the different types of e-resources available globally
- Chart out the Pros and Cons of e-resources

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A review of the literature was initially conducted to set the stage for the research.

- **Milind B. Anasane et. al, (2012)** states that Digital library services cover knowledge sources and meet the needs in diverse ways for readers by offering numerous repositories in knowledge tools, customized services, consortia, online tools, user's ability to operate by introducing new search techniques, knowing the importance of research content, library spaces close learning, Increasing university academic excellence by attaining high experienced performance levels. For professional training librarian involves aspects defining field planning strategies, the consequences of the information technology program, but in particular, underlines the development of new librarian working habits. Libraries are open to new technologies and the tools for content, human capital and facilities are factors for change.

- **Walmiki and Ramakrishnegowda (2009)** the findings of a evaluation carried out to know the acquisition of e-resources in Karnataka state university libraries are analyzed in this paper. The Internet facilities, the acquisition of CD-ROM repositories and online services, involvement have been preliminary in Consortium activities and e-resources which are available in university libraries through these consortium activities. The paper examines the challenges in university libraries to accessing e-resources. University libraries under the study have inadequate internet sites, low frequency, limited CDROM library acquisition and e-resources. Accessible scholarly article under the UGC-Infonet e-Journal Consortium is the only endurance of such university libraries, in terms of e-resource selection.

- **Hossaini (2017)** conducted a report on 'use and impact of electronic resources: a study on two selected academic libraries.' The methodology which is used in this research is found to be primary and secondary data collection. Primary data collected through survey questionnaire and secondary data collection through previous works of research. This research also focuses on the study of the effect of electronic resources on users. Thus Hossaini (2017) concludes that e-resources in intuitional libraries are still counting higher day by day. It is seen that e-resources in the library are taken over the conventional books in the library. It is also seen that there are pros and cons on the usage of e-resources as well.

- **Ananda (2017)** conducted a study on "use and awareness of electronic information resources among UG & PG students of T John College, Bangalore: A study." The study shows that 81 percent said they knew about Electronic Information Resources and 19 percent said they didn't know about Electronic Information Resources. The key aim of student use of Electronic Information Services is project research.

NEED OF E-RESOURCES

As is well known, learning is evolving from a traditional approach to a smart, digital one that makes use of new electronic devices. Today's tech-savvy students can access e-documents on any subject at any time and from any location. Therefore, the goal of the current study is to determine how effective electronic resources are in academic libraries.

EFFECTIVENESS OF E-RESOURCES

Information Technology (IT) has brought drastic improvements to education in the 21st Century. The conventional learning and teaching is progressively shifting towards online. Digital library, virtual

library, and e-library concept came into the current scenario. Resources of e-information has more convenience over conventional information services. Electronic tools are available in Web-enabled medium for teaching and learning. Lots of advancements in e-publishing have been observed in recent years. Publishers are involved in many topics such as cost printing, unstable readership, unstable user intention, maintaining archiving rights. Most scholars and corporate organizations are dedicated to the peer-publishing and quality assurance of different scholarly publications. Researchers are interested in easily accessing full text articles and connecting references across a dynamic space of knowledge. The objective of e-services is to make accessible to the user Information required for enhancing knowledge.

The Services include all services information, Workshops on library teaching, collections, and multimedia tools. The specific e-services services include remote provision access to and service delivery of library resources Library Information. According to laws, or Individual organizations rules, access may be limited to Members or to certain resources, such as commercial servers, with access only by participants by Password.

It choice to evaluate electronic library resources is located, is entirely used for research and study, libraries offer access to information in accordance with syllabus and keeping the library's traditional novelty material adds information, and offers new ways of informing users and paperwork. The expression "learn anywhere and anytime" is rooted in recent years, which clearly leads to the thought process of alternative information. College and High school the college library provided its services in accordance with the recipient users ' needs,

i.e. teachers, students and researchers. The current user faces a major problem regarding information modification. Because the user gets a number of relevant references because of "Information Explosion," they cannot justify which one is healthy. Therefore, an optimal structure

Reference library programs with well-defined learning objectives, trustworthy counseling, and a library will be supplied by the education program. where new technologies can be adapted through research and education. It should be kept in mind that a change in education and contextual knowledge won't have the same effect. All libraries continue to provide standard information services while periodically incorporating features for remote e-access. Web-OPAC (Online Public Access Catalogue) offers this option, which users can access from any location, including the library or a terminal that is connected to the Internet. This at last makes it possible to combine full-text documentation with bibliographic information. Anyone with access to bibliographic records—users, instructors, students, or researchers—can search for different kinds of keywords, topics, authors, titles, and regions.

A Library providing access to resources one of the library's

goals for collection development is the collection of references, the acquisition of databases and also the achievement of consortia to purchase periodicals online and provide users with access to resources. For effective management of e-resources, institutions need to have a maintenance team that monitors the resources hardware and software. Irritating problems can be minimized for instance: a doctor type a prescription message for the patient and tries to send to the pharmacy but the computer hangs and the message refuses to go. The doctor is forced to write the same message by hand for the patient and this is double work. Such a problem may have been caused by errors in the operating system and viruses which can be minimized or eliminated by regular servicing of the machines by the maintenance team. Even though ICT people are supposed to handle such problems, they are not always available.

It is well known that a student's learning and research and development at an institution can be subjectively impacted by their exposure to digital infrastructure. Quantitatively speaking, the quantity of articles, citations, inventions, research scholarships, consultancies, research studies, accreditations, and recognitions can determine an institution's research yield. Although it reflects the impact on the resources, the quantity of articles and citations they receive may be a more useful way to evaluate an institution's performance.

THE DIFFERENT TYPES OF E-RESOURCES AVAILABLE GLOBALLY TYPES OF E-RESOURCES DESCRIPTION

- **E-Book:** An e-narration of a printed edition that can be translated on a computer or a portable device specially built.
- **E-Journal:** An e-journal, also known as online journals, and e-serials, is originally full text, available in e-format.
- **E-Newspaper:** Often known as an online newspaper or digital newspaper that appears on the World Wide Web or the Internet is an E-newspaper.
- **E-Magazines:** The e-magazine or electronic magazine is an online magazine distributed on the World Wide Web. Some online magazines are called a webzine.

ONLINE INDEXING AND ABSTRACTING DATABASES:

- These are the reference sources that include journal bibliographic material including abstracts of the papers.
- **Online Full text database:** The full-text database is a collection of documents or some other content in the form of an archives where you can read, print or access the complete text of each referenced document online.
- **Online Reference database:** Various vendors and publishers now have various points of information

in electronic form through their repositories and websites such as yearbook dictionaries, encyclopedia sets.

- **Digital Image Collection:** An e-image is a photographic device that uses a sensor that is mounted behind a camera lens to convert an image into an electronic signal which can be stored on a disk or magnetic tape for playback on a VCR or video disk player and display on a Television.
- **E-Thesis and Dissertation:** This is an electronic document that describes the intellectual works or research carried out by scholars in a specific subject area and defines a certain period of time. Such documents are undoubtedly extremely valuable collections, especially in digital format, that qualify as an important component of a digital library.
- **E-Clipping:** The key purpose of e-clippings is to scan for new objects retrospectively and to evaluate them in full. It helps the users by simply clicking to get new images.
- **E-Patents:** The word patent generally refers to an exclusive right granted to somebody who invents any new, useful and non-obvious procedure, system, article of manufacture or composition of subject matter or any new and useful development thereof, and claims that right in a formal patent application
- **E-Standards:** Standards are output standards decided upon, or an accepted framework for a program to run. Professional standards prescribe the manufacture, description, calculation, or testing of materials and products according to established and agreed methods.

TYPES OF E-RESOURCES SERVICES

- Current Awareness Service (CAS)
- Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI)
- Document Delivery Services (DDS)
- Web-based Online Public Access Catalogue (WEB OPAC)

CURRENT AWARENESS SERVICE (CAS):

Informing library patrons about the latest arrival of books, journals, and other library materials is the goal of a library's current awareness service. In libraries, this is typically accomplished by circulating the printed list among departments and posting it on the notice board. This approach limits the information's dissemination and time constraints. These challenges are addressed by the E-CAS approach, which integrates CAS and SDI and periodically provides library users with new arrival information via email services.

SELECTIVE DISSEMINATION OF INFORMATION (SDI)

SDI is an information recovery technique that enables users to regularly receive pertinent information through profiles that represent their information needs.

DOCUMENT DELIVERY SERVICES (DDS)

Regardless of the location or type of the original, the Document Delivery Service (DDS) typically handles providing users with documents upon request, whether they are original or copies in print or non-print format. Electronic Document Delivery Systems (EDDS) are systems that receive and provide requests for documents using electronic technology.

WEB-BASED ONLINE PUBLIC ACCESS CATALOGUE (WEB OPAC)

A web-based online catalog of library resources is called Web OPAC. It is a library's main resource for finding content in its holdings. Web OPAC, when integrated into a library management system, allows users to browse and access the library collection remotely via the network. Web OPACs were also created as stand-alone online catalogs that could be accessed from a server by anybody in the world.

PROS OF E-RESOURCES:

- **Accessible and searchable:** Electronic resources are available 24x7 on / off campus, and can be easily searched using quick and easy-to-find advance search techniques. You may also search e-resources in full over an online index. Around the same time, many institutions and users will use the same services.
- **Links and Alerts:** The structure of the hypertext provides references to relevant documents and websites and frequent URLs for individual posts. Users are informed about the current developments published via email and other mode.
- **Inexpensive:** With regard to the printing and delivery costs, electronic tools are cheaper than printed materials. Electronic systems minimize staffing and maintenance costs associated with shelving and storage of items, both in traditional stack areas and in warehouses.
- **Flexibility:** E-journals grow rapidly. They are not bound or controlled by a specific network of formats, printers, or distributors.
- **No physical limitations:** The users of e-resources do not need to physically go to the library; users from around the world can access the same information as long as there is an internet connection.
- **Cost Effective:** The cost of electronic journals is reduced when compared to print journals due to paper eradication, printing, postage etc costs. The tough competition between publishers, the opening of new publishers in the market, the possibility of public e-journals, the advent of

e-libraries, consortia of libraries at local, regional, national and even international level, and thus when compared to all of these above mentioned factors electronic journal are cost effective.

- **Better Storage and Retrieval:** Digitally accessible knowledge has eliminated issues such as binding, shelving, storage, repair, etc. and creates incentives for better **storage & retrieval**.
- **Time Saving:** Time is saved in terms of digitally submitting research work to publishers, the same is submitted for peer review, selected/rejected or returned to authors for required modifications and finally by providing online access to libraries.
- **Excellent Searching Techniques:** The user will check the content/article using phrases such as and, or not (Boolean Operator) between words, up to, after etc.
- **Multi-user Access:** It is a wonderful gift of e-publishing that by subscribing to e-journals, book repositories, etc., many users can access the same material simultaneously from different locations in Internet.

CONS OF E-RESOURCES

Reading from screed or low-quality graphics can be uncomfortable. Access to e-resources necessitates computer and web skills. Depending on the speed of the Internet, e-resources can be downloaded and accessed.

Authenticity: When looking for a relevant e-resource online, a plethora of similar information appears against the useless ones. Authors who are concerned with broadly defining the sources and authority of information struggle to convince the reader of their legitimacy.

CONCLUSION

By using e-resources, the long-standing custom of "Everyday reader can get details at any time" is demonstrated. E-resources are useful for making sure knowledge is thorough and targeted. The user and library manage a variety of search options themselves with the help of the e-resources. The library can save space and user time by using e-resources. The information age is a fitting name for the current era. The importance of knowledge as a tool for a country's political, sociocultural, and economic development is becoming more widely acknowledged. In this digital age, libraries and knowledge centers heavily rely on electronic tools. This is primarily

caused by the volume of information, the accessibility of machine-readable information, increases in usage, storage capacity, etc. Electronic information services and the Internet

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